

Retention of ^{80}Br in Labelled Bromates following Isomeric Transition—Part II. Potassium, Calcium and Zinc Bromates

H. J. Arnikar and B. S. M. Rao

The present work deals with the studies of the retention of ^{80}Br following isomeric transition in labelled potassium, calcium and zinc bromates as a function of temperature over a wide range of -80° to 300° .

There is no appreciable change in retention due to thermal annealing, upto 100° the retention is 29%. This rises at 300° to 35%. This is in agreement with the results of earlier workers. However, a decrease is observed at lower temperatures, the retention at -80° being 25, 21 and 21% for potassium, calcium and zinc bromates respectively. The effect of cations on the retention is discussed. A mechanism is proposed to explain the results.

While much work has been done on the recoil effects following (n, γ) reactions in bromine compounds, only limited results are available on the chemical effects following the isomeric transition $^{80m}\text{Br} \rightarrow ^{80}\text{Br}$ specially in bromates. There is much uncertainty in regard to the nature of the primary fragments formed. Further, the results of the previous workers^{1,2} show certain discrepancies in thermal annealing of the effects due to isomeric transition in potassium bromate crystals. For instance, Campbell¹ did not observe any change in retention due to thermal annealing while Harbottle² reported a high retention even at 98° . Even on reinvestigation of the problem Campbell and Jones³ failed to resolve the apparent discrepancy. It was therefore considered of interest to see whether any annealing effects could be observed in other inorganic bromates. The study would also bring to light the effect of cations, if any, on the retention. The present work was undertaken to study the effect of thermal annealing on the retention of ^{80}Br in labelled potassium, calcium and zinc bromates.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) *Preparation of samples* : Calcium and zinc bromates were prepared by boiling a solution of their sulphates with an excess of barium bromate for several hours. After the removal of the insoluble barium sulphate the highly soluble calcium and zinc bromates were concentrated and purified by several recrystallizations at -20° for the complete removal of barium bromate.

A thermogravimetric analysis of zinc bromate showed that the loss of water of crystallization starts at 60° and continues up to 120° when two of the six water molecules are lost. The remaining four water molecules are lost between about 190° and 230° .

1. I. G. Campbell, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1959, **56**, 480, 665.
2. G. Harbottle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 805.
3. C. H. W. Jones, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Letters*, 1967, **3**, 363.

(b) *The labelling of the bromate* : All the materials used were of 'Analar' grade. The bromate was labelled with ^{80m}Br by dissolving the bromate in the water extract of neutron irradiated bromoform (using an ^{124}Sb -Be photoneutron source) and keeping the contents at 40° for an hour in 1 *M* nitric acid when the isotope exchange between bromine and bromate is very rapid. The bromate was then separated by acetone after extracting the free bromine with carbon tetrachloride. The labelled bromate was kept for 2 to 2.5 hr for isomeric transition to take place under appropriate conditions and allow ^{80}Br to grow to equilibrium. For the annealing experiments, samples were heated in an oil bath for temperatures up to 150° and in an electronically controlled furnace for higher temperatures maintained constant to within $\pm 2^\circ$.

(c) *Chemical separations* : The chemical separations were done by the method of Boyd *et al.*⁴ which depends on the rapid exchange between bromine and all valency states of bromine, except bromate. The labelled bromate was dissolved in 20 ml of distilled water and 10 ml of this were set aside for measuring the total activity. To the remaining 10 ml, 0.03 ml of bromine was added and extracted with three equal volumes of carbon tetrachloride making a total volume of 10 ml. Aliquot portions of the total and extractable activity were measured by a liquid G.M. counter. The retention, defined as the ratio of the activity of bromate to the total activity, was calculated after correcting for zero time, background and ^{80}Br activity. All the results were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

TABLE I

% Retention of ^{80}Br in labelled potassium, calcium and zinc bromates with temperature

Temperature (°C)	-80	-20	25	55	75	100	150	200	250	300
KBrO_3	25.3	28.4	28.7	—	—	29.0	33.8	33.8	36.0	34.5
$\text{Ca}(\text{BrO}_3)_2$	21.5	25.7	31.3	—	—	31.7	34.1	—	—	—
$\text{Zn}(\text{BrO}_3)_2$	21.0	22.9	31.4	33.0	33.5	53.4	—	—	—	—

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I shows the values of retention of ^{80}Br in labelled potassium, calcium and zinc bromates in the isomeric transition at various temperatures. Following are some of the important observations.

- (1) The retention at room temperature (25°) is about 29, 31 and 31% in crystalline potassium, calcium and zinc bromates respectively.
- (2) There is no appreciable change in retention on thermal annealing at higher temperature, upto 100° . This rises to 35% at 300° . However a decrease is observed at low temperatures the values being around 25, 22, and 21% for bromates of potassium, calcium and zinc respectively at -80° .
- (3) Retention in the solution state for the bromates of potassium, calcium and zinc are 20, 19 and 22% respectively.
- (4) Only in zinc bromate a high retention of 53% has been observed just at the melting temperature of 100° .

4. G. E. Boyd, J. W. Cobble and S. Wexler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 237.

In an isomeric transition, the emitted gammas are largely internally converted resulting in highly positively charged species by the Auger effect. The high positive charge on the bromine atom is quickly shared with the neighbouring oxygen atoms and the multi-centred charges end up in a coulombic explosion causing a rupture of the bonds in the parent bromate ion. However, the recoil energy in isomeric transition being about 370 cal/mole is less than the lattice energy. This cannot bring about considerable separation of the fragments. It follows that the fragments, being closer, should result in a greater degree of their recombination than in the case of (n, γ) reactions in which the fragments get separated further due to the greater recoil energy which exceeds the lattice energy. This view is supported by the results of Campbell¹ who reported higher retention values in isomeric transition than in (n, γ) reactions. The low retention values observed by Arnikaar *et al.*⁵ in several bromates following (n, γ) reaction also lend support to this view.

The retention of about 29% observed in KBrO_3 in the present work is same as that reported by Campbell¹. On the model of recoil annealing proposed by Jones³ the inherent crystal defects are helpful in promoting annealing. These defects have a shorter life time at higher temperatures. Failure to observe any change on heating appears to be due to the elimination of these defects on heating. This is in accord with the earlier results of Campbell¹ in KBrO_3 who did not observe any change in retention due to subsequent heating to 175°. The low retention at much lower temperatures observed by us is to be expected due to the restricted movement of the damaged fragments.

Experiments conducted in the solution state showed that the retention is some 10% less than in the solid state. This is to be expected as in the solution state the probability of the combination of fragments is less than in the solid state as they are farther apart and are surrounded by a solvent sheath.

The anomalous high retention of 53% observed in zinc bromate at 100° would suggest the occurrence of an isotopic exchange between the inert bromate and the active bromide fragments at this temperature when melting just begins. A further examination of this possibility is under study.

One significant result of this work is the effect of cations on retention. By a comparison of these results with our earlier results, 29% for sodium bromate and 34.5% for cadmium bromate, one can see that bromates of heavy metals have generally higher retentions than those of alkali metals.

The retention appears to increase with increasing ionization potential of the cation $\text{M}^{(n-1)+}$ to M^{n+} which is a measure of $\text{M}^{(n-1)+}$ ion to lose an electron. It is interesting to note that Saito *et al.*⁶ reported a similar dependence of retention of $^{80\text{m}}\text{Br}$ on the ionization potential of the cation in (n, γ) reactions of various bromates. This suggests the participation of cations in the redox reactions of recoil atoms. The cations of higher ionization potential may trap the electrons nearer to them. This permits a greater recombination of fragments with oxygen atoms or ions and hence a higher retention.

Department of Chemistry,
University of Poona,
Poona-7.

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6. N. Saito, F. Ambe and H. Sano, *Radiochim Acta*, 1967, **7**, 131.